

First Pādishāh Begum of the Mughal Empire: Āka-jānam Khānzādā Begum³⁸³

Unravelling the Veiled Histories of the Mughal Harem
by Analysing Literary and Visual Culture

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Abstract

The history of India will be synonymous with the grandeur of the Mughals and their significant contributions to the social, political, economic and cultural aspects of India, which are widely acknowledged and well-regarded. Like many other dimensions of human sociocultural existence, however, the craft of history-writing has also been synonymous with “his-story”. While a plethora of research has been undertaken on the lives of the great Mughal emperors, little is known about the women behind their lives and the role the harem collectively played in the political dynamic of the Mughal empire. Through this essay, I attempt to provide a biographical account of one such veiled woman—Khānzādā Begum, the elder sister of Bābur, the first Mughal emperor. A few scholars who know about her sacrifice of leaving her homeland and getting married to the ‘enemy’, the Uzbek Chief, Shaybānī Khān, have rightly characterised it as a key factor in the establishment of Bābur’s empire. An even lesser-known fact is that when she returned from her ‘exile’ from the Uzbek land, Khānzādā played a significant role on the political scene of her brother’s empire. Although she never penned a memoir, Khānzādā was mentioned or discussed in various contemporary accounts written by members of her family. Using primary sources such as Bābur’s autobiography “Tūzūk-i Bābrī,” Gulbadan Begum’s memoir “Aḥvāl-i Humāyūn Pādshāh,” Mīrzā Ḥaydār’s “Tārīkh-i Rashīdī,” and Shaybānī Khān Uzbek’s “Shaybānīnamah” and by analysing paintings depicting her, I argue that even though Khānzādā was deeply respected by many people, she was systematically obliterated from the records of one of the most documented histories, namely, the Mughal Empire, possibly because her sacrifice became a source of humiliation to the royal court. In the second half of this essay, I indicate some reasons why the Mughal harem has become synonymous with promiscuity in popular thought by reviewing contemporary accounts written on the Mughal harem in the pre-modern period as well as current historiography. I demythologise the term “harem” itself and analyse how royal women subtly exercised their political ambitions from behind the veil of the harem — which was a product of their genius as individuals as well as their Timurid heritage.

³⁸³ An early version of this research has appeared as “Behind the First Great Mughal: Khanzada Begum” in the KMC Journal of Asia, 2022. I am grateful to Dr Ankur Barua, Senior Lecturer, University of Cambridge and Mrs Poonam Devasher, Former Head of Department, MCM DAV College, India, for reading the drafts of this paper. Thanks are also due to the reviewers at Carnival for their input and the participants of all conferences for their comments.

Keywords: Mughals – Khānzādā Begum – Harem – Visual Culture – Veiled History

Image 1: Genealogy of Khānzādā Begum (1748–1575).

Introduction: The Myth of the Harem

“For many,” Annemarie Schimmel writes in *The Empire of the Great Mughals: History, Art and Culture*, “The Taj Mahal, the lily-white mausoleum built by Shāh Jahān for his wife Mumtaz Mahal symbolises Mughal India, in fact, the whole of India.”³⁸⁴ Shāh Jahān, the distraught Mughal emperor, has become an eternal symbol of grief and the departed wife who had the “greatest symbol of love”³⁸⁵ built for her the ideal of a beloved companion from a bygone era — an image quite at odds with the role women played in the Mughal harem, the name ascribed to the secluded living quarters of the womenfolk of Muslim emperors and kings. A similar style of romanticisation applies to various other pre-modern Muslim dynasties. However, in many of these social contexts, princesses played a much more active role than simply sitting pretty within the comforts and luxury of the harem, a place which came to be regarded as a “sequestered, sexualised domain” for all the womenfolk of the emperor in the Western fantasy.³⁸⁶ Indeed, according to F. Mernissi, “After the

³⁸⁴ Annemarie Schimmel, *The Empire of the Great Mughals: History, Art and Culture* (London: Reaktion, 2004), 143.

³⁸⁵ “Taj Mahal: The Symphony of Love,” *Google Arts & Culture* accessed November 27, 2023, <https://artsandculture.google.com/story/taj-mahal-the-symphony-of-love/WAUxKuf8iRyglA>.

³⁸⁶ Reina Lewis, “The Harem: Gendering Orientalism,” in *Orientalism and Literature*, ed. Geoffrey P. Nash, 166.

Mongol invasion [under Genghis Khān], the thrones of Muslim states were occupied by an impressive number of women with privileges of the *Khutba*³⁸⁷ and the coining of money.”³⁸⁸

This, one must be mindful, was particularly true for the nomadic Mongols, and not their contemporaries in the Perso-Islamic world. As M. Szuppe observed, “Turco-Mongol nomadic cultural tradition³⁸⁹, as compared with Irano-Islamic customs of settled people, gave a much larger place to women's social and political activities and family blood ties on both paternal and maternal sides... Among the Mongols and Īl-khānids [of the thirteenth and fourteenth centuries] ... women were entitled to a share of war booty and had the right to participate in the *quriltay*, the all-Mongol assembly. Not only did they become regents of their minor sons, but also under certain circumstances, they could themselves lay claim to the throne. Even after Islamisation progressed among the Turco-Mongol tribes, women retained much of their social position.”³⁹⁰ For example, the Kutlugh-Khānid dynasty in Kimran, Persia. In the fourteenth century, this province was ruled by Kutlugh Khātūn (also called Turkhān Khātūn in some documents) and later by her daughter Pādishāh Khātūn (also mentioned as Safwat al-din Khātūn).³⁹¹

Beyond the Mongols, one finds examples of female leadership in the Arab world. In Yemen, after the advent of Islam, even though several women held political power, the names of Malika Asma and Malika ‘Arwa from the eleventh century stand out, for they alone enjoyed the unquestioned privilege of the head of state, namely, the *khutba* was proclaimed in their name in the mosques. Mernissi notes that no other “Arab women had this honour in any Arab country after the advent of Islam.”³⁹² Closer home, that is, in India, one is reminded of Raziya Sulṭān. A thirteenth-century ruler of the Mamlūk Dynasty of the Delhi Sulṭāns in Northern India, chosen purely on talent, her femininity became her greatest obstacle in ruling the Sultanate. So, she is said to assumed to discarded the “female attire” entirely — she sat in the open without a veil and wore the “trappings of masculinity” in body and spirit.³⁹³ No other instance of any lady Sulṭān in the Delhi Sultanate is found thereafter. Her successors, the Mughal princesses, though influential, did not go so far. The Mughals in India did not even have a woman installed as the *Pādishāh*, that is,

³⁸⁷ *Khutba*- Prayers which acknowledge the legitimate ruler of the kingdom uttered at the time of the weekly congregational Friday prayers. (See Richards, *The Mughal Empire*).

³⁸⁸ Fatima Mernissi, *The Forgotten Queens of Islam*. (Minneapolis: Univ. Minnesota Press, 2009), 99.

³⁸⁹ Dr Ankur Barua, in personal correspondence, noted that this relative form of greater independence and power enjoyed by the ‘nomadic’ Turco-Mongol women vis-à-vis the ‘settled’ Iranian women was also possibly true of women in “early” Vedic semi-nomadic milieus (c.1500 BCE), although not in “established” Vedic societies (c.200 CE).

³⁹⁰ Maria Szuppe, “Status, Knowledge and Politics: Women in Sixteenth Century Safavid Iran,” in *Women in Iran: From the Rise of Islam to 1800*, eds, Guity Nashat and Beck Lois, 141.

³⁹¹ Mernissi, *Forgotten Queens*, 99.

³⁹² Mernissi, *Forgotten Queens*, 123.

³⁹³ Alyssa Gabbay, “In Reality a Man: Sultan Iltutmish, His Daughter, Raziya, and Gender Ambiguity in Thirteenth Century Northern India,” *Journal of Persianate Studies*, 4 (January 2011): 1, 45- 63.

emperor (save perhaps Nūr Jahān, who, Ruby Lal claims acted as a co-sovereign with her husband Jahāngir (r.1505–1527 CE), the fourth Mughal emperor).³⁹⁴ Nonetheless, the harem played, from the outset of the Mughal empire, i.e. c.1500 CE, a significant role in its socio-political dynamics. The tradition of a strong female presence started with Bābur himself, the first Mughal emperor.

Zahiru'ddīn Muḥammad Bābur (1483–1530 CE) came from, what the fifteenth century Central Asia is regarded, as an enviable and distinguished lineage. A Timurid (descendant of Tīmūr) on his paternal side and a Chingissid (descendants of Chingis Khān) on his maternal side, Bābur was only eleven years old when he ascended the throne of Fergana (a valley in present-day Uzbekistan) in 1494 CE. His tender age was not the only problem; Bābur had inherited an extremely unstable empire. By the late fifteenth century, a struggle between members of three lineages - The Timurids, The Chaghatai Mongols and Uzbeks ensued over control of the *Mā warā' al-Nahr* (Transoxiana) region, once entirely under Tīmūr's son Shāhrukh (r.1407–1447), and which had by the 1490s been divided among these three political powers. To complicate matters, animosity brewed between the Timurids themselves. Bābur's father, Umar Shaykh Mīrzā (d.1494 CE) was one of the four brothers descended from Tīmūr's third son, MiranShāh. For Bābur, contestation also came from the Chaghatai Mongols, whose leader was his maternal uncle, Mahmud Khān (d.1509). However, the greatest threat to both the Timurids and Mongols came from Shaybānī Khān, the Chinggisid leader of the powerful Turko-Mongol Uzbek tribal confederacy who had originated in Qipchaq Steppe and had a stronghold in Merv [present-day Turkmenistan]. The Uzbeks had been raiding Timurid territories for decades before they began moving towards the principal Timurid territories in *Mā warā' al-Nahr* and Iranian Khorāsān, precisely when Bābur's reign began.³⁹⁵

In such a precarious political situation, the young Bābur was strongly guided by his maternal grandmother, Aisan Daulat Begum (d.1505 CE).³⁹⁶ A woman of extraordinary intellect, she acted as a regent to Bābur after his father died. She legitimised his accession when there were doubts about a mere boy being able to rule while the 'Uzbek threat' loomed large. Bābur acknowledges this influence in his "*Tūzūk*" (diary), also called the "Vaḡayī" (events):

"Few women were my maternal grandmother's equal in judgement and counsel. She was very wise and farsighted, and most of my affairs were conducted with her advice."³⁹⁷

³⁹⁴ See Ruby Lal, *Empress: The Astonishing Reign of Nūr Jahān* (Delhi: Penguin Viking, 2018).

³⁹⁵ See Stephen F Dale, *Babur: Timurid Prince and Mughal Emperor, 1483–1530*. (New Delhi: Cambridge University Press, 2018), 34–35.

³⁹⁶ Also spelled as 'Esan' Daulat Begum in some texts.

³⁹⁷ Dilip Hiro, ed., *Bābur Nama: Journal of Emperor Bābur*, translated by Annette Beveridge (Gurgaon: Penguin Books, 2006), 19–20.

A Mughal painting from the late sixteenth century commemorating the significant influence that the Aisan Begum enjoyed exists (see image 2). Note the body language of the main characters—Bābur (left) and his grandmother Aisan Daulat Begum (right). As opposed to the standard rules of gender, it is the young boy here who is sitting with his body slightly inclined— as if searching for his grandmother’s approval whilst the grandmother sits upright, her hand below her chin as if contemplating the final decision. Also, note the facial expressions of the women who surround them— who probably constituted the council of Aisan Daulat Begum— many weighing in on the discussion, some even contributing to it.

In this context, we should also note Bābur’s mother, Qutlugh Nigar Begum (d.1505 CE), who accompanied him on several campaigns across Timurid land and later into Hindūstān. However, the most underrated woman in Bābur’s harem was his elder sister Khānzāda Begum, who is today called the “First Lady of the Empire.”³⁹⁸ The most surprising aspect of Khānzāda’s life is how little is written or known about her even when her brother Bābur, most known for his autobiography and conquests, is one of the most studied personalities in an extensively discussed period of Indian history.³⁹⁹ No details about her birth and childhood exist except her birth year (1478 CE). This essay, built on a study of some primary and secondary sources, will trace her life from 1500 CE, that is when she was in her early twenties (since this is when a mention of her is first found) to her death in 1545 CE, and also present arguments as to why she has remained “veiled” to present-day historians despite her remarkable contributions to her brother’s empire. A separate section is devoted to understanding, critiquing and decoding the Mughal harem by discussing other women of the harem.

³⁹⁸ Schimmel, *The Empire of the Great Mughals*, 145.

³⁹⁹ Although, neither Bābur’s mother nor grandmother have yet been subjects of intense research, they still find due mention in contemporary records — their names are known and their contribution acknowledged. As Dilip Hero notes in the introduction to the *Tūzuk-i Bābrī* or the *Bāburnāma* (“Book of Babur”): “Women are conspicuous in the *Babur Nama* by their absence. Sure enough, they appear in the text as wives, grandmothers, aunts, concubines and slaves. But they are little more than shadowy figures — bar one: Babur’s maternal grandmother Aisan Daulat Begum ...” See Hiro “Introduction,” *Bābur Nama: Journal of Emperor Bābur*, xxxi.

Image 2: “Bābur Seeks His Grandmother’s Advice,”
painting from the *Baburnama*, ca. 1590–92 CE, 44 x
29,4 cm.

The Life of Khānzādā Begum (1478–1545 CE)⁴⁰⁰

A Narrative of Sacrifice and Exile

In 1500 CE, the seventeen-year-old king of Fergana seemed to have done the impossible: amidst intense political tension and competition, Bābur had somehow occupied the prized Tīmūrid territory, Samarkand (a city in present-day Uzbekistan). However, this success was short-lived. Soon, Bābur was surrounded by the troops of “his greatest rival, the Uzbeks, led by the formidable Mohammed Shaybānī Khān.”⁴⁰¹ (See image 3) With no reinforcements or help, Bābur was at the Khān’s mercy. It is in these circumstances that we first hear of Khānzādā: for the vanquished Bābur was offered ‘peace’ only if his sister was betrothed to the Uzbek Chief.⁴⁰²

Image 3: Portrait of Muhammad Khan Shaibani, the Uzbek (d.1510), opaque watercolour and gold on paper, ca. sixteenth century.

⁴⁰⁰ Also spelled as ‘Khānzadeh’ Begum in some texts.

⁴⁰¹ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama*, xv.

⁴⁰² Dale mentions that this matrimonial alliance was accepted only after their mother Qutlugh Nigar Begum had approved. Although *Shaybānīnāma* calls it a “love-match,” Bābur’s fear of acknowledging this marriage can only be seen as a compromise for which Khānzādā paid. See Dale, *Babur*; Sunita Sharma “The Exponential Role of the Women Protagonists in the Formative Years of Babur — Linkages Revisited,” *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress*, 361–62.

Bābur's narrative is slightly different: "Umar Shaikh Mīrzā's eldest daughter was Khānzādā Begum, my full sister, five years older than me. When I had come to abandon Samarkand in 905 AH/1500 CE after a five-month siege by Mohammed Shaybānī Khān (Uzbek), she *fell* to him."⁴⁰³ It is certain that when the twenty-three-year-old Khānzādā "fell to the enemy," she was not an unmarried woman. In a separate entry, Bābur clearly notes: "As soon as Mohammed Shaybānī Khān Uzbek captured Herat, he took Muzaffar Mīrzā's wife, Khānzādā Begum...and married her, ignoring the *adat* [al-'idda: religious decree in Islam], according to which remarriage is unlawful within a certain period of divorce or widowhood."⁴⁰⁴

Shaybānī Khān also divorced his previous wife, Khānzādā's maternal aunt, Mihr Nigar Chaghatai, to marry Khānzādā. Together the couple had a son, Khurram Shāh (c.1501–12 CE).⁴⁰⁵ Dale argues that although Shaybānī Khān assured peace, Bābur did not believe in his word.⁴⁰⁶ Nonetheless, Khānzādā was still left behind with the "enemy" and the rest of Bābur's harem was allowed to leave the occupied city unharmed – a truce made possible only because of what I characterise as her "sacrifice" on the planes of realpolitik.

Against this historical backdrop, I argue that Bābur's silence about his sister's role in these peacemaking engagements in an otherwise lucid and detailed autobiography has nothing to do with women being *pardah-gīyan*.⁴⁰⁷ If that were the case, Bābur would not have specifically mentioned his grandmother Aisan Daulat Begum or his beloved wife Māham Begum either. Therefore, I read this silence as an indication of his embarrassment relating to his failure to protect his sister. While brothers are traditionally supposed to be protectors of their sisters, he offered his sister as a sacrificial goat for his and his clan's safety. As Mīrzā Ḥaydār, a cousin of Bābur, declares unequivocally: "Bābur Pādishāh gave up Khānzādā Begim in exchange for his own life and escaped."⁴⁰⁸

Sunita Sharma believes that Khānzādā had been treated well during her marriage to Shaybānī Khān owing to her highly respected Timurid lineage. However, Sharma calls this forced matrimony a "mismatch" owing to the couple's cultural differences and political animosity, causing

⁴⁰³ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama*, 12.

⁴⁰⁴ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama*, 184.

⁴⁰⁵ Khurram was entrusted with the territory of Balkh when he was about five years old (c.1505), he died at the age of twelve. See Sharma, "Exponential Role," 361–2.

⁴⁰⁶ Dale, *Babur*, 56.

⁴⁰⁷ As Mika Natif wrote, "The notion of invisibility and seclusion of Mughal ladies from the male eye due to *pardah* [veil] is related to their rank and status at the Mughal court." This began steadfastly with the reign of Akbar (r.1556-1605). *Pardah-gīyan* meant both literal and metaphorical exclusion of women from public view. See Natif "Preliminary Thoughts on Portraits of Mughal Women in Illustrated Histories," in *Reflections of Mughal Art and Culture*, ed. Roda Ahluwalia, 45.

⁴⁰⁸ As quoted by Ira Mukhoty, *Daughters of the Sun: Empresses, Queens and Begums of the Mughal Empire*. (New Delhi: Aleph, 2018), 6. Mīrzā Ḥaydār, who wrote *Tārīkh-i Rashīdī*, was Bābur's cousin and was with him in Kabul. See Bamber Gascoigne, *A Brief History of the Great Moghuls* (London: Robinson, 2002), 250.

a lot of anxiety to Bābur and their mother, Qutlugh Nigar Begum. However, since no records devoted to Qutlugh Nigar Begum exist, it is difficult to gauge how she might have reacted to this matrimonial alliance.⁴⁰⁹

Reunion with Kinsmen

In one of the retellings of Khānzādā's life, Khānzādā is depicted as voluntarily deciding to stay back in Samarkand for her clan's safety. However, we will probably never know how she responded to this forced matrimony, because we do not have a memoir or diary of her.⁴¹⁰

Image 4: What the journey might have looked like, tracing Khānzādā's migration from 1500–1510 CE.

⁴⁰⁹ Sharma, "Exponential Role," 361–62.

⁴¹⁰ Here, I am specifically referring to a newspaper article in the Children's editorial. See, Pavithra Srinivasan, "Heroine's Tale," *The Hindu*, June 28, 2019, sec. "Children," <https://www.thehindu.com/children/heroines-tale/article28201559.ece>.

We hear of Khānzāda only a decade later when Bābur notes:

“In 916 AH/1510 AD, she was in Merv [Turkmenistan today] when Shāh Ismā'il [of Iran] defeated Shaybānī Khān Uzbek. For my sake, Shāh Ismā'il treated her well, giving her sufficient escort to Qunduz [Afghanistan today] where she rejoined me. When I went to see her, neither she nor those around her knew us, although I spoke. They recognised us after a time.”⁴¹¹ (see image 4)

Bābur notes that he learnt of the news of Shaybānī Khān's death when his Timurid cousin sent a messenger with the news also telling him that 20,000 Mongols – previously subjugated by the Uzbeks – had arrived in Qunduz. It is at this junction that Khānzāda Begum arrived in Qunduz. According to Azfar Moin, Shāh Ismā'il later used “this favour” he had done to Khānzāda, and her brother Bābur, to exact the latter's help in conquering Samarkand since Bābur was a Timurid, who was experienced and motivated in taking this important city in Transoxania. Bābur did deliver on this promise in 1511 CE albeit not very successfully, for he was able to occupy Samarkand only for a brief time before he was ousted again within a few months of his arrival.⁴¹²

This reunion has been captured in an imaginative portrait commissioned by Akbar, much after both Bābur and Khānzādā were dead (see image 5). According to Mehreen Chida-Razvi, this painting is one of the earliest representations of elite women in the Mughal court. While the figures lack “individualisation” – no unique facial features are drawn for any character in the painting (this artistic evolution, that is, the development of verisimilitude portraiture, happened under Jahāngir and continued under the patronage of his son Shāh Jahān⁴¹³) — it is the symbolic attributes that make this painting significant for our purposes in this essay. In a clear departure from the precedent set for royal paintings and portraits in Central Asia, it is not the emperor, but his sister who occupies the central stage. Khānzādā is depicted holding a commanding hand high in the air, while the rest sit around her reverently.

Her figure overshadows everyone else in size including her brother, the emperor Bābur — a clear acknowledgement of her sacrifice by the royal court and more significantly by her descendants.⁴¹⁴ Khānzādā Begum, now nearly thirty-three years old (considered middle-aged in the

⁴¹¹ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama*, 12.

⁴¹² Azfar Moin, *The Millennial Sovereign: Sacred Kingship and Sainthood in Islam*. South Asia across the Disciplines (New York: Columbia University Press, 2012), 84. Upon personal correspondence with Dr Moin, he further explained that the Shāh of Iran stood to benefit immensely from this favour he had done to Bābur, because the Safavids, like most Central Asian kingdoms at that time, worked mostly through vassal relationships, especially if this were to govern places far from their capital cities. Political alliance with Bābur, who had occupied Kabul by now and was looking to India as well as was clearly not strong enough to challenge the Safavids, was almost an ideal alliance.

⁴¹³ Mika Natif, *Mughal Occidentalism: Artistic Encounters between Europe and Asia at the Courts of India, 1580-1630* (Boston: Brill, 2018), 205-260.

⁴¹⁴ The comments about the size of figures in the portrait are my own. Comments by Chida-Razvi were taken from her lecture on “Women and the Arts at Mughal South Asia.”

Mughal era) returned as a twice-widowed lady. Shaybānī Khān, mistrustful of her loyalty, had divorced her within a couple of years of their marriage. Scholars argue that this divorce happened because the Begum overtly supported her brother in the Uzbek court. Nonetheless, Shaybānī Khān “gave her” (i.e. married her off) to another official in his court, Sayyid Hada.⁴¹⁵

Hada later died along Khān’s side in the Battle with the Shāh of Iran in 1510 CE. It was in the aftermath of this battle that Khānzādā returned to her brother aided by the Shāh of Iran. Soon after, Khānzādā was married again, and this time to Mahdī Khwāja, one of Bābur’s most trusted *begs* (noblemen) who had fought in the Battles of Panipat (1526 CE) and Khanwa (1527 CE) and was also made the commandant of Etawah and Bianah (towns in present-day Uttar Pradesh).

Image 5: Painting from the *Baburnama*, Ladies of the Court in an Encampment outside a Citadel, ca. 1590 CE, painted in watercolour on paper, 25,4 x 14 cm.

⁴¹⁵ Sharma, “Exponential Role,” 361.

According to Beveridge, Khānzādā could have been married to Khwāja anytime between 1510 and 1519 CE, a period of which no record is known to have survived, including the most important source on Khānzādā, her brother's diary, *Tūzūk-i-Bāburi*.⁴¹⁶ No information on progeny from this union exists.

Moreover, the future of this marriage is unclear because Khwaja had opted to leave Hindūstān for Kabul when Bābur permitted his nobles to do so after his decisive victory in 1527 CE.⁴¹⁷ However, it is certain that Khānzādā had not left Hindūstān with Khwaja. In a correspondence written in February 1529 CE, Bābur clearly states: "I have summoned my elder sister [Khānzādā] and wives to Hindūstān... Directly as this letter arrives, you must get [them] out of Kabul ..."⁴¹⁸

Image 6:
The Princes of the
House of Timur,
attributed to Mir
Sayyid Ali ca. 1550–
1555 CE, paint on
cotton, 108 x 108,5
cm.

⁴¹⁶ Hiro, ed., *Bābur Nama: Journal of Emperor Bābur*, 12.

⁴¹⁷ There is some confusion among historians over the nobles Khānzādā married. Dale argues that Sayyid Hada was Khānzādā's second husband and Mahdī Khwāja her third. (See Dale "Bābur," 96; 156). Sharma believes that Khānzādā was married to Mahdī Khwāja when she was betrothed to Shaybānī Khān and that on her return the marriage was renewed. See Sharma "Exponential Role," 361. However, in Beveridge's *Bāburnama* the first husband mentioned is one "Muzaffar Mīrzā." See Beveridge, (1902), 1.

⁴¹⁸ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama: Journal of Emperor Bābur*, 327-328.

Rise to Power and Later Years

Khānzādā's return to the harem⁴¹⁹ was not deeply contested or stigmatised. On the contrary, she was held in the highest esteem. In the winter of 1530 CE, when Bābur knew his end was near, he had asked Khānzādā to arrange marriages for his daughters, Gulrang Begum and Gulchira Begum, instead of the girls' mother (i.e., Dildār Begum) or his favourite wife Māhim Begum. Bābur was succeeded by Humāyūn in 1530 CE. It was in 1532/33 CE, about twenty-two years after her return, Khānzādā became the first "Pādīshāh Begum," the principal lady of the palace of her nephew and the second Mughal Emperor, Humāyūn (1508–56 CE). As Pādīshāh Begum, Khānzādā arranged for celebratory feasts (called *tüy*)- a Timurid symbolic tradition through which senior women in the harem exhibited their influence and authority.⁴²⁰

Khānzādā steered the celebrations for the wedding of her nephew Hindāl (*tüy-i Mīrzā Hindāl*) in November 1533 CE.⁴²¹ Hindāl's bride, Sulṭānim, the younger sister of her third husband, Mahdī Khwāja, who was now Khānzādā's sister-in-law, had been under Khānzādā's care since she was two years old. Gulbadan Begum, Bābur's daughter, writes about her aunt in her memoir titled *Aḥvāl-i Humāyūn Pādīshāh*⁴²² in these terms:

"Āka-jānam had taken care of Sulṭānim as though she were her child... Khānzādā Begum gave everything she had collected, and she arranged a feast such as had not been made for any other child of my royal father. She planned it all and carried it all out."⁴²³

⁴¹⁹ Harem, an anglicisation of the Arabic term "haram" (tr. a sanctuary), was a space where the womenfolk of the emperors and ruling elite lived. The harem was a residence to their wives, sisters, mothers, daughters as well as concubines and the maidservants. The space of the harem was sacred and only the ruler/noble or those men he most trusted were allowed access. Interestingly, especially in India, the practice of sequestering the women, i.e. establishing the harem, was also adopted by the non-Muslim nobles and provincial rulers. It must be noted that the connotations of the Arabic "haram" is markedly different from the English "harem" — which has evolved over centuries to become synonymous with scandal, especially for the "Gunpowder Empires": the Mughal Padshahs of India, the Safavid Shahs of Iran and the Ottoman Sultans of Turkey. For a detailed discussion about the Mughal Harem and the evolution of its meaning, see page 110 of this article.

⁴²⁰ *Tüy* (or *tooy*): A Central Asian-Timurid institution observed by the Early Mughals was a celebration to mark important events like weddings or circumcision where patrons provided food and entertainment over several days followed by games. See Ebba Koch, *Planetary King: Humayun Padshah, Inventor and Visionary on the Mughal Throne*. (Ahmedabad: Mapin Publishing, 2022), 125.

⁴²¹ There is some discrepancy amongst scholars about the date of Hindāl's wedding. Koch (2022) notes that it is November 1533, whereas Parodi (2007) dates it to 1534. I am using the date mentioned in the most recent publication, i.e. the one by Koch. See Koch, *Planetary King*, 125 and Laura Parodi "Of Shaykhs, Bibīs and Begims," 7, 13, 18.

⁴²² The *Aḥvāl-i Humāyūn Pādīshāh*, also called *Humāyūnnāma* ("the Book of Humāyūn") was written by Gulbadan Begum (d. 1603 CE), the third daughter of Bābur. It is the first female-authored account of life at the Mughal Court. R. Gould notes, "Although best classed as historiography, the *Book of Humāyūn* is a genre-crossing historiographic memoir. It dwells not on battles and royal genealogies, as did its male-authored predecessors, but rather on domestic scenes of birth, death, anger, love, and other aspects of daily life, especially as experienced by women." See Rebecca Gould, "How Gulbadan Remembered: The *Book of Humāyūn* as an Act of Representation". *Early Modern Women: An Interdisciplinary Journal* 6, 186-187.

⁴²³ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama*, 125-126.

Gulbadan gives a detailed list of the lavish gifts Khānzādā presented to the couple which included nine sets each of jewellery, shawls, robes, handkerchiefs, towels, cushions, horses with jewelled saddles, parasols, slaves of Ethiopian, Circassian, Turkish descent, and so on. The inauguration of the Mystic Palace⁴²⁴ (*tūy kbāna-i tilsim*), built in Agra on the banks of river Yamuna happened around the same time as Hindāl's wedding. This inauguration was celebrated before the wedding: this procedure does not seem to follow protocol but was a decision entirely in Khānzādā's hands – this is another indication of the significant authority she enjoyed. Ebba Koch in her most recent scholarship describes the seating arrangement in detail:

“At both festivals [inauguration and wedding reception], the main gathering took place in the first octagonal hall [of the Mystical Palace in Agra] ... In the vestibule (*pīshgāh khānā*) of the central octagonal hall, Humāyūn sat with his aunt Khānzādā Begum on a gem-studded throne (*takht-i-murassa*) ...”⁴²⁵

The authority to answer questions as who organised the feast, who sat closer to the *Pādishāh*, the order of the feasts, etc., reflected one's seniority in the harem. Although Koch notes that Khānzādā had presided over the celebrations in place of Māhim Begum (Humāyūn's birth mother and Bābur's chief queen) who had died in May 1533, this was probably because Māhim had adopted and raised the groom, Hindāl, just as Khānzādā had raised Sulṭānim and not because the former held any precedence over the latter. Khānzādā had probably been declared “*Pādishāh Begum*” during Māhim's lifetime. The dynamic becomes clearer on close reading of Gulbadan's memoir. In this conversation between the Emperor and the Begum over scheduling the feasts (as recorded by Gulbadan), note how Khānzādā helms the entire discussion — subtly overpowering the Emperor, Humāyūn, himself:

“Dearest lady (Khānzādā Begum) said to his Majesty [Humāyūn]: ‘When will you make Mīrzā Hindāl's marriage feast?’ His Majesty replied: ‘B’ismu-l-lah.’ When Mīrzā Hindāl was married, my lady (Māhim) was living, but there was a delay in arranging the feast.

According to Ruby Lal, the original memoir uses the word “Akum,” which has wrongly been translated by Annette Beveridge as “My lady” or “Dearest Lady” in her translated works. Lal argues that ‘Akum’ was a more personal term of address than that. See Ruby Lal, “Historicizing the Harem,” 601.

In her most recent scholarship, Ebba Koch furthers this argument and states that Gulbadan called Khānzādā by the same epithet as her father Bābur – since *Āka-jānam* was probably a Turkish title for “my elder sister.” See Koch, “Planetary King,” 125.

⁴²⁴ The Mystic or Talismanic Palace is called “the most intriguing of Humāyūn's inventions.” Khwandamir, a chronicler in Humāyūn's reign refers to it as “pleasing palace” and “delightful palace” — its reconstruction has proven difficult. Abu'l Fazl, Akbar's court chronicler never mentions the palace probably because its layout was too “eccentric” for him. It was possibly devoted to Humāyūn's occult interests. For a detailed discussion of its architecture, see Koch, *Planetary King*, 123–37.

⁴²⁵ Koch “Planetary King,” 125.

(Khānzādā Begum) said: ‘The things for the Mystic Feast are also ready. Let us first celebrate this, and afterwards Mīrzā Hindāl’s.’ His Majesty said: ‘Let whatever my royal aunt wishes be done.’ She replied: ‘May God bless it and make it good.’⁴²⁶

Even though no painting commemorating Hindāl’s wedding or inauguration of the Mystic Palace exists, in the painting titled *The Princes of the House of Timur* (see image 6), one of the few paintings commissioned and painted in Humāyūn’s reign depicts a celebration in motion. Although, it was severely overpainted under subsequent Mughal emperor to include their likeness, for the purpose of this essay, the original setting and roles are crucial. Originally titled “Humāyūn’s Garden Party,” it depicts a reception by Humāyūn for his closest followers, as indicated by the characteristic headgear worn by Humāyūn and his guests — the *Tāj - i ‘Izzat*, a hallmark for special favour in Humāyūni court. Note the seating arrangement — sitting in the garden pavilion, Humāyūn now faces three of his descendants — Akbar, Jahāngir, Shāh Jahān all added in the seventeenth century. Also note the elaborate cooking arrangements in the background, helmed by servants in Central Asian clothes.⁴²⁷ Dating this unnamed celebration depicted has proven difficult, however, if this celebration were organised under Humāyūn before 1545, it would undoubtedly be organised by Khānzādā.

Her most significant political contribution, however, was her mediation between her warring nephews. In the 1540s, when Kāmṛān and Askari had rebelled against their brother Humāyūn, it was Khānzādā who the *Padishah* (Humāyūn) had requested to intervene. Ruby Lal gives a detailed description of this episode: “Khānzadeh Begum travelled from Jun to Kandahar.... Kāmṛān urged [Khānzādā] to have the *Khuṭba* read in his name. She advised him as follows: ‘As His Majesty (*Firdaus-makāmī*) [Bābur] decided and gave his throne to Emperor Humāyūn, and as you, all of you, have read the *Khuṭba* in his name till now, so now regard him as your superior and remain in obedience to him.’⁴²⁸ Such was her authority within the harem that when Kāmṛān had approached Dildār Begum (Bābur’s widow, Hindāl and Gulbadan’s mother, Kāmṛān’s stepmother and a highly respected figure in the Mughal court) with the same request, that is, to have the *Khuṭba* read in his own name, Dildār Begum promptly asked him to convince Khānzādā first.

According to L. Balabanlilar, this intervention was ultimately unsuccessful. Nonetheless, Khānzādā, apparently for her unflinching support for Humāyūn, was appointed as the ambassador

⁴²⁶ Gulbadan Begum, *The History of Humāyūn: Humāyūn-nama*, translated by Annette S. Beveridge (London: Royal Asiatic Society, 1902), 117–118.

⁴²⁷ Crill Rosemary and Kapil Jariwala, *The Indian Portrait: 1560-1860* [Exhibition, London, National Portrait Gallery, 11 March-20 June 2010] (Ahmedabad: Mapin publishing, 2010), 50.

⁴²⁸ Ruby Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2005), 61.

of the territory between Kandahar and Sindh, shortly before her death.⁴²⁹ Indeed, according to Sharma, Khānzādā was “the first woman from the Mughal dynasty [who was] entrusted with the official diplomatic task. The trend set by her was followed in later times.”⁴³⁰

According to Gulbadan’s memoir, when the Mughals had to flee from their Empire after Shēr Shāh Suri took over in 1540 CE, unlike the other harem inmates who had chosen relatively safer places like Lahore or Sindh, Khānzādā had chosen to follow Humāyūn who was on the run from the Afghani Shāh. Perhaps a last act of bravery, the sixty-seven-year-old Khānzādā travelled from Sindh to Kandhar to negotiate safe passage for Humāyūn through the Safavid territories. She probably died soon after, because Beveridge notes that Khānzādā died at Qabal-Chak [Kandahar?], “after a life full of sorrows and chagrin” in 1545 CE.⁴³¹ Parodi mentions that Khānzādā died at Gilchak [Qabal-chak] while accompanying Humāyūn on his way to Kabul (she had been sent by Kāmṛān as a mediator).⁴³² According to Misra, “except Khānzādā Begum, there does not seem to be any other lady who played any significant role in contemporary politics during the reign of Humāyūn.”⁴³³ Today, this powerful woman lies buried along with her brother Bābur, nephew Hindāl and niece Gulbadan in the *Bagh-i Bābur* (Gardens of Bābur) in Kabul, Afghanistan; with Khānzādā buried on a higher terrace, reserved for female burials.⁴³⁴ The *Bagh-i Babur* continued to be used as a cemetery for select members of the Timurid family long afterwards.

How “Feminist” was Khānzādā Begum? - A Discussion

Upon discussion about Khānzādā, a question I have commonly encountered from discussants is that if she was indeed empowered to officiate on certain public occasions, why did she not step out of a system founded on various types of androcentric presuppositions? Why did she not become independent, instead choosing to remain “veiled” behind the emperors — her brother and later her nephew?

⁴²⁹ Lisa Balabanlilar, “The Begims of the Mystic Feast: Turco-Mongol Tradition in the Mughal Harem,” *The Journal of Asian Studies* 69, no. 1. (2010), 133. According to Gulbadan, this appointment was made ‘for her service of peace between Kāmṛān and Humāyūn, after the latter had returned from his Persian exile (1545)’. See Hiro, *Bābur Nama: Journal of Emperor Bābur*, 34) Interestingly, Ebba Koch notes that when Humāyūn succeeded to the throne, he faced opposition from a high-ranking amir who wanted Mahdī Khwāja, Khānzādā’s third husband to become the next *Pādīshāh*! However, we find no mention of Khānzādā supporting her husband’s succession to the throne. See Koch, “Planetary King,” 31.

⁴³⁰ Sharma, “Exponential Role,” 362.

⁴³¹ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama*, 251.

⁴³² A reverse mediation tactic seems to be in play here: it seems as if Khānzādā now [ie in 1544–45] mediated for Kāmṛān, who had inherited the Kabul region. Humāyūn, who had lost the throne of Hindūstān by now to Shēr Shāh, probably desired that his brother hand over Kabul to him, which Kāmṛān refused — just three years after he had reluctantly settled in Kabul — wanting to become *Pādīshāh* instead. See Parodi “of Shaykhs, Bibīs and Begims,” 131.

⁴³³ Rekha Misra, *Women In Mughal India 1526-1748* (Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal Publishers, 1967), 20.

⁴³⁴ Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 32. Gascoigne wrongly mentions, “two of his [Bābur’s] children Hindāl and Khānzādā are buried nearby ...” Whereas it should have been sister and son or “Hindāl” and “Gulbadan.”

Scholars in the field of women's studies often encounter questions of this type. The scholarly exercise of retrieving the voices of women such as Khānzādā may be categorised as “feminist history,” but this description would be problematic — not only since the English word “feminism” originated sometime during the nineteenth century, but also because the European sociocultural frames from within which it emerged were significantly different from those of Mughal India.

Certainly, women have been marginalised in societies everywhere—be it in the past or the present. However, unlike in some Western social contexts, where feminists have taken the radical step of criticising marriage as an institution, sometimes even calling for its abolition, the case in contemporary India is different.⁴³⁵ For instance, in some rural settings, women who “rebelled,” by eloping with lovers despite being married, were not hunted down or killed upon being caught but were re-absorbed into the social network after an elaborate “purification” process — her “bad behaviour” attributed to the machinations of an “evil spirit.” This way, the system could continue without its cracks bursting open.⁴³⁶

A popular female reaction against social oppression emerged in the voice of Mirabai, a Rajput princess who did not obey her husband or immolate herself on his funeral pyre, but, adopting the simple lifestyle of a widow, intermingled with some male saints. According to R. Varghese, she resisted the norms that “limit a woman to her role as a domesticated woman, a silent woman...The Mira, who spoke, became the collective voice of the marginalised after she was popularised through literary renditions” —Mirabai's social trajectories indicate some possibilities of opposition available to elite women in north-western India in the sixteenth century.⁴³⁷

In both cases, India or Europe, some women have indeed exercised their their agential capacities in various settings – however, if we were to view Khānzādā from the “premodern” Mughal Empire as “feminist” in its literal, dominant sense, without contextualising the term, we may be disappointed or disillusioned. The significations of the term “feminism” can vary significantly across the field of critical feminist theory, and it should not be applied uncritically to past epochs or non-European social milieus.⁴³⁸ However, feminism is not the only European idea

⁴³⁵ Clare Chambers, “Feminism, Liberalism and Marriage,” (previously “Recognising Marriage as a Symbolic Institution,” unpublished paper, Brown University, 2013) accessed May 12, 2024, <https://www.brown.edu/Research/ppw/files/Feminism,%20Liberalism%20and%20Marriage.doc>.

⁴³⁶ I am thankful to Dr Priyatosh Sharma, Head of Dept of History, Panjab University, India for sharing this insight into rural social culture and practices from his fieldwork in the hills of Northern India.

⁴³⁷ Ritu Varghese, “Mirabai in Popular Imagination: Reading Bhakti Canon in Contemporary Context,” *Artha Journal of Social Sciences* 19, no. 2 (2020): 74. It should be noted that Mira was indeed a Rajput princess who had rebelled. However, most of the stories/legends now ascribed to her in popular thought have transformed her into a literary tradition — the coalescing rebellion of several women in sixteenth-century North-West India.

⁴³⁸ Here, it is important not to essentialise “feminism.” There is a wide spectrum of feminist standpoints in contemporary critical studies. According to *some* of these standpoints, Khānzādā was sufficiently feminist for her times.

which should not be superimposed onto Mughal India; likewise, we should not unreflectively project our contemporary notions of “secularism,” “toleration,” and “orthodoxy” onto the reign of emperors such as Akbar, Aurangzeb, and others.⁴³⁹ Thus, in our case, the expectation that a Mughal princess would openly revolt against a patriarchal system would be far-fetched — this is not to say that Khānzādā was not capable of doing so, but simply that such a rejection was not required of a woman of her time. She had readily been accepted back into the court despite her “tainted past” of being married to the “enemy” and she enjoyed a very comfortable and powerful position within the social space of the harem.

This exploration of the meanings of feminism leads us to another significant question: if the harem was an important social arena where some women exercised their prestige and authority, what factors are responsible for the notoriety one popularly associates with the harem today? To understand Khānzādā’s achievements, demythologising the harem becomes important and to do so, one must, at this juncture, step back from Khānzādā’s life and analyse the harem and its prejudices as a whole.

Demythologising the Harem

Interrogating the Prejudices: “Haram” vs “Harem”

In one of the few academic studies on the Mughal harem, note how the scholar describes the space of the harem:

“The Mughal harem conjures up a vision of a sequestered place ensconcing beautiful female forms in mysterious magnificence. It was indeed made so by the great Mughal Emperor Akbar ... He brought in a large number of inmates to adorn it. He provided them all kinds of luxuries and made elaborate arrangements for their seclusion and security...The inmates of the harem dressed well, ate well and tried to enjoy as possible...Elder ladies would not have shared with the young ones their problems of life or secrets of love; talk about sex was taboo for the young in the medieval world ... Still, let us say that the young girls were not exposed to all the celebrations in the Mahal in which sex orgies dominated or the master bargained for beauty and love on occasions like Nauroz and Khushroz ... Naturally, every lady of consequence tried to win the master’s undivided love and openly competed to gain ascendancy in the harem. Women’s beauty gave them power as undefined as unique.”⁴⁴⁰

⁴³⁹ Richard Maxwell Eaton, *The Lotus & the Lion: Essays on India’s Sanskrit & Persianate Worlds* (Delhi: Primus Books, 2022).

⁴⁴⁰ KS Lal, *The Mughal Harem* (New Delhi: Aditya Prakashan, 1988), 19,135.

For another scholar notes:

“Noble households were divided into the external, more public areas, dominated by men, and the interior, secluded space reserved for women ... The wives, concubines, and female relatives of the *master* were ranked by seniority, blood ties and favour in a strictly prescribed hierarchy. Ideally, the harem provided a respite, a retreat for the nobleman and his closest male relatives — a retreat of grace, beauty, and order designed to refresh the males of the household.”⁴⁴¹

Even though Nath cautions his readers in his work *Private Life of the Mughals of India* that “It is a general misconception that every woman of the Mughal *harem* served a sexual purpose ...”⁴⁴² The promiscuity that is generally associated with the harem (apparent also in the title of this work), is also visible here, for Nath notes that:

“... it goes to the credit of the Mughals that they could manage their harem efficiently... It was Akbar who founded the customs, traditions and institutions which guided and regulated the course of Mughal life and culture ... Though Akbar never indulged in excessive sex, he had a taste for young beautiful women whose company he liked ... Jehangir was a sensuous person and he excessively indulged in both wine and women ...”⁴⁴³

As Ruby Lal remarks in the introduction of her pioneering work on the Mughal Harem, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, “This account might be dismissed as the view of a somewhat traditional historian, were its assumptions not so widely and consistently shared.”⁴⁴⁴ Harem, an anglicisation of the Arabic term “haram” that means “a sanctuary,” it is also related to the word “harim,” meaning female members of the family and “haraam” meaning forbidden.⁴⁴⁵ However, the connotations of the Arabic “haram” is markedly different from the English “harem” — which has evolved over centuries to not only refer to a secluded building occupied by elite Muslim women shielded from the public, but has also notoriously become synonymous with scandal – a place where a promiscuous “Emperor was surrounded by thousands of nubile young women competing for his attention.”⁴⁴⁶

The origin of “harem” can be dated to the late sixteenth and the early seventeenth century — this was the time of significant internal and external developments. Internally, the Mughals had begun consolidating their power in India, their residence became “more permanent” and even

⁴⁴¹ John F Richards, *The Mughal Empire* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 1993), 61–62.

⁴⁴² Ram Nath, *Private Life of the Mughals of India (1526 - 1803 A. D.)* (New Delhi: Rupa, 2005), 19.

⁴⁴³ Ram Nath, *Private Life of the Mughals of India (1526 - 1803 A. D.)* (New Delhi: Rupa, 2005), 11, 19, 28, 29.

⁴⁴⁴ Ruby Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2005), 2.

⁴⁴⁵ Jonathan Gil Harris, *The First Firangis: Remarkable Stories of Heroes, Healers, Charlatans, Courtesans & Other Foreigners Who Became Indian* (New Delhi: Aleph Book Company, 2015), 152.

⁴⁴⁶ Ira Mukhoty, *Daughters of the Sun: Empresses, Queens and Begums of the Mughal Empire* (New Delhi: Aleph, 2018), xi.

though the women became restricted to the secluded quarters of their harem, this did not alter their importance or role in imperial traditions like the *tüy*.⁴⁴⁷ Simultaneously, this was also the time when the West began taking an increasing interest in India: missionaries and travellers flocked to the “Moghul Empire” in large numbers and constituted the first of the “eye-witness accounts” of India. The “Harem” particularly had caught their fancy since it was veiled from the public. For example, an English merchant William Finch (d.1613) imagined Jahāngir in the harem “like a cock of the game... where he may crow over all.”⁴⁴⁸ In another instance, Father Rudolf Aquaviva, one of the Jesuit missionaries from Italy, who had tried albeit unsuccessfully to convert Akbar to Christianity wrote letters back home explaining the reasons of his failure, one of which was:

“He [Akbar] has so many hobbies and at least a hundred wives...Part of the time he spends with the numerous women he keeps in his house, so that he has no time available to care for what is of consequence to him ...”⁴⁴⁹

Thus, the failure to convert was blamed at the emperor’s weakness of character, women being one among several reasons responsible. Here, one must remember that the focus for the missionaries was propagation of Christianity, and not the harem, thus comments about women appear hurried and indiscriminate. No effort was made, for example, by the missionaries to contextualise Akbar’s “hundred wives” — a product of fostering political unions to win allies in expanding the Mughal Empire, than for pleasure. As M. Moneta remarks, “European [witnesses] were not inclined or able to decipher the contents and values of this [Mughal] civilisation...and failing in their attempts to impose their own ideas, they (especially the missionaries) soon developed a superior attitude ...”⁴⁵⁰ As a final case study, note how Francisco Pelseart, a Dutch merchant, who travelled to India in early seventeenth century, described the Mughal harem:

“Their mahals [harem] are adorned internally with lascivious sensuality, wanton and reckless festivity, superfluous pomp, inflated pride, and ornamental daintiness ...”⁴⁵¹

Most of these assumptions were based largely on market gossip since seldom were stranger men allowed into royal women’s residences. Only the most trusted European physicians (only two - Nicolò Manucci and François Bernier) working in the mid-eighteenth century, were allowed on rare occasions to treat the royal women. Manucci, who worked as a physician in the Mughal court

⁴⁴⁷ Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 22.

⁴⁴⁸ As quoted by Gil Harris, *The First Firangis*, 153.

⁴⁴⁹ As quoted by Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 33.

⁴⁵⁰ Marco Moneta, *A Venetian at the Mughal Court: The Life and Adventures of Nicolò Manucci* (Gurugram: Vintage, an imprint of Penguin Random House, 2021), xi.

⁴⁵¹ As quoted by Nath, “Private Life,” 30.

in the late seventeenth century, describes the procedure of tending to the women of the harem in detail, how he was never allowed to see his royal patients:

“I did my utmost to get an examination before I began the treatment. Mohammedans are very touchy in the matter of allowing their women to be seen, or even touched by the hand; above all, the lady being of royal blood, it could not be done without express permission from the king ...”⁴⁵²

Even the seemingly “first-hand” witnesses did not have access to the harem to properly be able to view and study its culture. This lack of access did not stop Manucci and others from commenting on the lifestyle of the harem. Thus, the description of the harem so offered is disapproving and sometimes even titillating:

“Some of the women in the harem, being shut up with this closeness and constantly watched, and having neither liberty nor occupation, think of nothing but adorning themselves. Their minds dwell on nothing but malice and lewdness... There are some who from time to time affect the invalid, simply that they may have the chance of some conversation with, and have their pulse felt by, the physician ... The latter stretched out his hand inside the curtain; they lay hold of it, kiss it, and softly bite it ...”⁴⁵³

Some of these accounts later formed the basis of the earliest history books penned by British colonial writers in the nineteenth century.⁴⁵⁴ This is precisely how paintings like the one drawn by Stifter (see image 7) who had not have even travelled to India, let much alone visited a harem, gained currency and legitimacy in popular European imaginations. Scholars believe that much of current-day prejudice springs from the European and Orientalist perspectives — reiterated and repeated so often in traditional histories of India (as in the three excerpts from books written in late twentieth century), that they were accepted as the truth. As Jonathan Gil Harris aptly remarks in his work, *The First Firangis*: “What exactly is the harem? Perhaps the most accurate answer is that it is a space of western fantasy ... The space of the has morphed into something rather different in the Western Imagination than what it was in reality.”⁴⁵⁵

⁴⁵² As quoted by Moneta, “Venetian at the Mughal Court,” 79.

⁴⁵³ As quoted by Moneta, “Venetian at the Mughal Court,” 91–92.

⁴⁵⁴ For example, James Mill writes in his well-known *The History of British India* (1815), “It is not surprising, that grossness, in idea and language, respecting the intercourse of the sexes, a uniform concomitant of the degraded state of the women ...” or Stanley Lane-Poole writes in *Aurangzib* (1893): “His [Shāh Jahān] favourite wife [Mumtaz Mahal], the lady of the Taj, had died in 1631, in giving birth to their fourteenth child and her husband had centred his affection upon his eldest daughter, Jahanara, with so much fervour as to cause no little scandal, while he also denied himself none of the more transitory joys of the zenana ...” For a more detailed discussion on the European perspective on the Mughal harem, see Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 25–49.

⁴⁵⁵ Gil Harris, *The First Firangis*, 152.

Image 7: *In the Harem*, attributed to Moritz Stifter, ca. 1890, oil on panel, 33 x 40,7 cm.

Image 8: *Birth of Prince Salim*, attributed to Bishandas, ca. 1620, ink, colour, gold and silver on paper, 38.9 × 29 cm.

Decoding the "Real" Harem

Now that we have established that the harem, contrary to some colonial tropes, was a dynamic space (called *Mahal* in the Mughal period), it is also important to note that it was not entirely devoid of controversies. The task of decoding these intricacies is especially difficult owing to the meagre first-hand sources available to us: Gulbadan Begum's memoir *Aḥvāl-i Humāyūn Pādshāh*, being the only exception until now.

Scholars believe that harem was instituted under the Mughals only after Akbar, the third Mughal emperor, ascended the throne. Nath argues that the peripatetic residences of the first two Mughal emperors, Bābur and Humāyūn, made of tents and ravaged by poverty⁴⁵⁶, did not technically qualify as a harem: not just because the number of women who cohabitated with the emperors was much smaller, also because during their reigns "harem" was a technical term for a stationary and ordered institution which was governed by rules and officers.⁴⁵⁷ These peripatetic women's quarters were in line with the "Timurid" way of living, which the Mughals, especially, Bābur and Humāyūn, had "clung on to relentlessly."⁴⁵⁸ A vivid description of the Timurid living space by Ruy Gonzales de Calvijo, a Castilian envoy to Tīmūr's court in 1404, gives us an idea of the luxurious encampments that the womenfolk of Tīmūr lived in, which the Mughals, as direct descendants had inherited:

"... [there] is erected an awning of many coloured silk cloth: this shades the door, and prevents the sun from shining on any one at the place of entrance: further this awning can be moved about to face this way or that, and so keep the sun's rays from falling within the tent. Of these two great Enclosures with many tents within them is that belonging to the chief wife of Tīmūr, who is known as the Great Khānum or Lady, while that second Enclosure belongs to his second wife who is called the Kuchik-Khānum, meaning the Little Lady ... All of these Enclosures were occupied either by the wives of Tīmūr, or by the wives of his grandsons, and these princes and princesses have their abode therein, as does also his Highness likewise, both summer and winter."⁴⁵⁹

⁴⁵⁶ For example, in the aftermath of the Battle of Chausa, fought between Humāyūn and Shēr Shāh in 1539, as Humāyūn fled for his life, his eight-year-old daughter Aqiqa Sultan Begum drowned and three of his wives went missing. See Laura E. Parodi, "Of Shaykhs, Bibīs and Begims: sources on early Mughal marriage connections and the patronage of Babur's tomb," *Mediaeval and Modern Iranian Studies: Proceedings of the 6th European Conference of Iranian Studies (Vienna, 2007)*, eds. Maria Szuppe, Anna Krasnowolska and Claus Pedersen, *Cahiers de Studia Iranica* 45 (2011), 128.

⁴⁵⁷ Nath, *Private Life*, 25-26. Kishori Saran Lal also attributes the small size of the Harem to their nomadic and short reigns. See Kishori Saran Lal, *The Mughal Harem* (New Delhi: Aditya Prakashan, 1988), 19-20.

⁴⁵⁸ Balabanlilar, "The Begims of Mystic Feast," 127.

⁴⁵⁹ Ruy González de Clavijo, *Embassy to Tamerlane: 1403-1406* (London: Routledge Curzon, 2005), 127-128.

In these luxurious garden encampments, the Timurid begums hosted elaborate feasts, drank alcohol in mixed groups with men and wore the “thinnest of gauzes” that allowed the observer to clearly see their features.⁴⁶⁰

Thus, the respect that the Mughal harem enjoyed was also unique to their heritage. Scholars have repeatedly stressed on the Timurid tradition making it possible for women to be independent in the Mughal harem. As Balabanlilar notes, “even through the stable and highly institutionalised years of the Mughal seventeenth century, at a time when the public roles of their contemporaries, Ottoman and Safavid dynastic women, were becoming increasingly limited and narrow, the dynasty’s allegiance to Timurid culture and values remained central to their imperial institutions, and the walls of the royal harem of Mughal India remained, for the most part and for generations, porous and nuanced in the model of their Timurid ancestors.”⁴⁶¹

It can, therefore, be assumed that the womenfolk of Bābur and Humāyūn, like the focus of this study, Khānzādā Begum, were quite independent individuals. Though they observed *pardab* (veil) which did invariably signify some measure of seclusion, they certainly enjoyed more freedom than the womenfolk of the preceding rulers, namely, the Delhi Sultanate. Ashraf even claims that Humāyūn’s womenfolk freely mixed with male friends and visitors, and some of them dressed in male garments and played polo.⁴⁶² This is not to say that the Mughal women of the later centuries, ie the descendants of Bābur and Humāyūn, did not enjoy influence. The “covert methods of participation” mentioned above had slightly transformed as the enclosure became cemented.

According to N. Arbabzadah, this “high status” enjoyed by the women of the Mughal harem also granted them the ability to play a significant role in religious life through patronage—aided as much by their Turco- Mongol heritage, as by the tenets of Islam. “The Sharī‘ah laws of inheritance and property, enabled them to have their own private wealth and...the importance of almsgiving (*ṣakat*) as one of the main pillars of Islam further encouraged such patronage activity

⁴⁶⁰ Even though Babur ruled “by lineage and in the tradition of Tamerlane,” a slight shift in culture had certainly taken place. For example, almost a century after Clavijo feasted and drank alcohol with Timor’s wives and daughters-in-law, Bābur, wrote in astonishment at a woman’s request to join him at his drinking party [*majlis-i sharb*] because he had never seen a woman drink before. This is not to say that “conservativeness” had crept into the harem of Timūr’s descendants, but just to caution that whilst Bābur may have embraced Timurid traditions, with time, norms in the harem had changed. Other Timurid traditions, for example, organising Tūy by important women of the harem or the importance of maternal lineage had continued unaltered. See Balabanlilar, “The Begims of Mystic Feast,” 126-130.

⁴⁶¹ Balabanlilar, “The Begims of the Mystic Feast,” 126.

⁴⁶² KM Ashraf, *Life and conditions of the people of Hindūstān (1200-1550 A.D.): Mainly based on Islamic sources*. (New Delhi, India: Gyan Pub. House, 2000), 170. Ashraf was in particular referring to two women - Shad Begum and Mihrangaz Begum who, Gulbadan avidly describes were “adorned by various accomplishments, such as the making of thumb-rings and arrows, playing polo and shooting with the bow and arrow...” According to L.Balabanlilar, Gulbadan’s acute interest in these women suggests that these “polo-players, dressed in male garments” women were not a social norm in the Mughal harem. However, what is more noteworthy is that these women were not treated as eccentrics, but were honoured guests at the royal family’s feasts. See Balabanlilar, “The Begims of the Mystic Feast,” 125.

by adding a dimension of religious duty to the elite practice of patronage. These traditions later continued among Timurid women in Mughal India, as in the case of Princess Jahānara (d. 1681 CE), the daughter of Shah Jahān and patron of various Sufis, who was buried at the Sufi shrine of Nizam al-Din Awliya (d. 1325), in Delhi.⁴⁶³

Jahānara Begum, for example, patronised a mosque for a spiritual guide, Mullah Shāh Badakhshi in Srinagar and another Jami Masjid (congregational mosque for the Friday prayers) in Agra. However, it is the inscription on the central ivan of the Agra mosque, which gives us another example of how royal women expressed their “power” and “prestige” through socially acceptable means, for the inscription notes:

“It [the Jami Masjid] was built by her order who is high in dignity, who is as elevated as the firmament on which it sits, screened with curtains bright as the sun, possessing a glorious palace as illuminated as her wisdom, veiled with chastity, the most revered of the ladies of the age, the pride of her gender, the princess of the realm, the possessor of the three domes as worldly crowns, the chosen of the people of the world, the most honoured of the issue of the head of the Faithful, Jahānara Begum.”⁴⁶⁴

Bokhari notes that though the mention of a “princess’s name” as well as profuse eulogisation in a public building in the capital city is a certain indication of how ineffectual the *ulema* (Islamic theologians) had become by Shāh Jahān’s reign in mid seventeenth century (r. 1627 - 1658), it is more telling of how an imperial female could be transparently present — her veil almost not visible — when she presented herself as a spiritual exemplary.

This visibility of females becomes especially important, since a deliberate anonymisation of the imperial women in the official chronicles had begun earlier.⁴⁶⁵ Placed behind their grand titles: for instance, Ḥamidā Bānū Begum, became “Maryam Makānī” after her son Akbar became emperor; Jahāngir’s Rajput mother, was called “Maryam uz Zamani and the harem was collectively called *ʿIsmat qubab* (“cupola of chastity”)⁴⁶⁶ and ensconced within the tall walls of the harem guarded by faithful of eunuchs, Mughal princesses gained an education in calligraphy, poetry and the Qur’an, usually under a governess addressed as “Atun Mama.” Gulbadan, Salima Sultān, Nūr Jahān, Jahānara are a few outstanding and prominent female scholars of this royal house. Mughals princesses were magnificent calligraphers too. Folios of the Qur’an, calligraphed by Zeb un-Nisā’

⁴⁶³ Nushin Arbabzadah, “Women and Religious Patronage in the Timurid Empire,” in *Afghanistan’s Islam*, ed. Nile Green (California: University of California Press, 2017), 71.

⁴⁶⁴ Afshan Bokhari, “The ‘light’ of the Timurid: Jahān Ara Begum’s Patronage, Piety, and Poetry in 17th-Century Mughal India,” *Marg, A Magazine of the Arts* (2008): 55.

⁴⁶⁵ Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 183.

⁴⁶⁶ Akbarnamah as quoted and translated by Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 182.

and Zinat un-Nisā', Aurangzeb's daughters, in the Nasq script, have also been found.⁴⁶⁷ Many of these princesses, along with other non-royal, educated women of the harem (milk-mothers?) would participate in secluded poetry recitations (Mušā'ira). Jahānara authored two texts, *Mu'nis-al-Arwāḥ* and *Risālah-i Šāḥibīyah* about her involvement with Sufi orders, in addition to patronising architecture (as discussed above).⁴⁶⁸ Many princesses, as noted earlier, remained spinsters as Mughal Emperors could not find grooms "worthy" of their daughters. However, those who did get married, usually did so much later than girls from ordinary households of that time. For example: 'Āi'sha Sulṭān, Bābur's first wife and daughter of his paternal uncle, Sulṭān Ahmad- Mīrzā, though betrothed to him at five, only began cohabitating after she had turned sixteen. All of Bābur's daughters were married between thirteen to nineteen — as opposed to the public who married their daughters between six to ten years.⁴⁶⁹ Subsequently, as the empire expanded, Mughal princesses remained unmarried — for example, Jahānara Begum and Roshanara Begum, Shāh Jahān's daughters. This was more because the Mughals, as emperors of the land, would not marry their womenfolk to less aristocratic households; since no royal family existed in Hindūstān which could match their prosperity, some Mughal princesses ended up as spinsters rather than making the choice to be one. In mediaeval Indian society, the status of a woman reached its zenith when she became a mother. Mothering a prince, "the source of continuity of the dynasty" was especially a different kind of a maternal role "since the woman also had to be a bodyguard — necessarily suspicious and paranoid, ever vigilant to threats against her son's life and always apprehensive about possible traitors close by..."⁴⁷⁰ Under the Mughals, stepmothers, foster mothers, milk-mothers and at times even mothers of an enemy were treated with veneration. For instance, Bābur is said to have provided "a mansion, revenue worth 70,000 *tankas* and servants" to the mother of his rival, the slain Sulṭān Ibrahim Lodhi, even though she had tried to poison him.⁴⁷¹

This is where some complexities come into play for even motherhood was not without hierarchy in the harem. According to Natif, amongst the royal mothers, those who bestowed "Timurid" or "Persianate" prestige upon the Mughal bloodline held a higher status and enjoyed more powerful positions in the court.⁴⁷² For example, in her article, *Of Shaykhs, Bibis and Begims*, Parodi convincingly argues that Humāyūn's fixation on marrying Ḥamīda Bānū was not the

⁴⁶⁷ The folios can be accessed at the Khalili Collections, QUR 417, fold. 1b-2a and fold. 197b-198a.

⁴⁶⁸ Even though poetry recitation and writing were in keeping with the Timurid tradition, the female literary voices in the Mughal world were few. Women came into their own when the Persian hegemony broke, and Urdu and Hindi recitations became popular in the late eighteenth century. See Sunil Sharma, *Mughal Arcadia: Persian Literature in an Indian Court* (Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, 2017), 31–32.

⁴⁶⁹ Sudha Sharma, *The Status of Muslim Women in Medieval India* (New Delhi: SAGE, 2016), 48–49.

⁴⁷⁰ Munis D. Faruqi, *The Princes of the Mughal Empire, 1504–1719* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 68, 72.

⁴⁷¹ Sharma, *The Status of Muslim Women in Medieval India*, 64–65.

⁴⁷² Natif, "Preliminary Thoughts," 40.

outcome of a “romantic *coup de foudre*” but a political convenience, since Ḥamīda Bānū was a descendent of the Shaykhs of Jām and for Humāyūn, who had by this time lost his empire to Shēr Shāh, this alliance with the lineage of Aḥmad-i Jām (who the Ṭimurids had patronised throughout the fifteenth century) was the best way to reassure his followers.⁴⁷³ This connection, Parodi writes, “also accounts for the saintly aura posthumously attributed to Humāyūn, upon which Akbar [the third Mughal emperor and son of Humāyūn and Ḥamīda Bānū] based his own claims to spiritual charisma, reinforced but not exclusively provided by his maternal descent.”⁴⁷⁴ Thus, spiritual pedigree was equally honoured.

This hierarchy became more pronounced once Mughal emperors began marrying local Indian princesses, who ended up being relegated to a lower position, much less dignified than the wives who came from Central Asian and Ṭimurid lineage, as a consequence of Akbar’s ‘Rajput Policy’ (cultivating marital alliances with native royal families). For example, in the painting the *Birth of Prince Salīm* [the future Jahāngir], (see image 8), note how Ḥamīda Bānū, the Mughal Mother with “Persianate” pedigree is centre-stage (seated on the chair), whereas, the new mother, a Rajput Princess, the future Queen Mother, is relegated to the sidelines even though it is the birth of Jahāngir that is depicted here. Better lineage, also meant a better position as a wife to the *Pādishāh*. For example, Bābur’s first marriage to his paternal cousin fell apart in three years — this was because his wife Āi’sha’s “left him.”⁴⁷⁵ Though this signified the importance that wives enjoyed in the harem, one must not forget that the authority to take this decision was possible only because Āi’sha was of a respectable lineage.⁴⁷⁶ However, above all existential or social factors, the one that contributed the most to a woman’s prestige was wisdom gained through experience, which is probably why Khānzādā became the *Pādishāh* Begum and not one of Humāyūn’s wives.

As Ruby Lal notes: “The respect that Dildār and Khānzādā acquired was one that came with age. This is a point that emerges repeatedly in the narratives. It was the senior generation that was revered, especially influential mothers, not the ‘favourite’ wives.”⁴⁷⁷ The harem was not a space meant to enhance the individual ambitions of women, certainly not those of innovative young

⁴⁷³Laura E. Parodi, “Of Shaykhs, Bibīs and Begims: Sources on Early Mughal Marriage Connections and the Patronage of Babur’s Tomb,” *Mediaeval and Modern Iranian Studies: Proceedings of the 6th European Conference of Iranian Studies (Vienna, 2007)*, ed. Maria Szuppe, Anna Krasnowolska and Claus Pedersen. *Cahiers de Studia Iranica* 45 (2011), 127.

⁴⁷⁴ Parodi, “Of Shaykhs, Bibīs and Begims,” 130.

⁴⁷⁵ Parodi, “Of Shaykhs, Bibīs and Begims,” 128.

⁴⁷⁶ The reason for this decision could either be the death of their only child, a daughter, Fakhr-un-Nissa, a month after her birth or Bābur’s behaviour with Āi’sha, or perhaps both. By his own admission, Bābur writes, “I was not ill-disposed towards her [Āi’sha Sulṭān]. But this being my first marriage, out of modesty or bashfulness, I used to see her once in fifteen days or so.” See Hiro, *Bābur Nama*, 60.

⁴⁷⁷ Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 125.

women. But it was a place where women could take pleasure in everyday exchanges, in watching the stars, in gazing at the flow of the Jamuna ...⁴⁷⁸

Conclusion

The essay sought to establish two things: one, provide a biographical account of a Mughal princess almost forgotten both in the Mughal world as well as current-day scholarship — Khānzādā Begum (1478–1545).

I argued that this absence in contemporary records, the most important being her brother Bābur’s diary, has indirectly become an acknowledgment to her significant yet humiliating “sacrifice” in 1501 CE — getting married to the “Timurid enemy,” the Uzbek chief, Shaybānī Khān. Ultimately, this “sacrifice” made the foundation of Mughal empire possible in Hindūstān, twenty-five years later. Even though she remains relatively undiscussed in literary records, the visual culture of Mughal world — paintings and portraiture, proved helpful in analysing Khānzādā’s relevance to future emperors of the empire. Khānzādā’s life and subsequent return to her brother’s empire ten years later after “exile” in the Uzbek land, was never stigmatised. She was made *Pādīshāh* Begum — the principal lady of the Mughal harem and her roles and responsibility transcended the realms of the harem — and included counselling the emperor and acting as his representative, as Khānzādā did for her nephew Humāyūn towards the end of her life.

In the second section of the essay, we took a step back from Khānzādā’s life and analysed the space that she belonged to and subsequently became the supervisor of — “the Harem,” an anglicisation of the Arabic “haram” and discussed how apart from the corruption in spellings, the connotations and significance of the space also changed with the arrival of the Europeans, who unfamiliar with the concept of the “haram” and debarred from entering its premises soon began to weave fanciful narratives — reiterated so often in scholarships, that they were accepted as the truth well until the end of the twentieth century.

My ongoing research on the life of Khānzādā Begum has led me to realise that several statements used to describe the harem both in contemporary European accounts as well as the traditional history books are ideologically and factually wrong. In the excerpts reproduced in the section “Interrogating the Prejudices,” note the use of the term “master” to describe the relationship between the emperor and all inmates of the harem — inherently associating subservience with the ladies — a direct contrast to how, for example, Bābur relied on the counsel

⁴⁷⁸ Lal, *Empress: The Astonishing Reign of Nūr Jahān*, 98.

of his grandmother, or *Pādishāh* Begum Khānzādā guided Emperor Humāyūn or came to his aid during rebellions.

Thus, women of the harem, especially the Mughals, did participate in the functioning of the empire, however, owing to the sequestered nature of their living (which became pronounced once Akbar ascended the throne, as sacrality was imposed on the women's quarters ⁴⁷⁹) or perhaps due to the supposed "passive participation"⁴⁸⁰ expected from women due to their gender — these women often devised a complex and covert method of participation. By acting as diplomats or counsellors to the emperor or by taking up the "domestic" tasks of arranging important feasts, these women developed some ingenious ways of exercising their ambition in political matters, while never compromising on their "sacred seclusion" i.e., the harem. This is ultimately what I learnt during the course of my research and is what this essay hopes to have highlighted by now,

However, to properly understand the harem in the Mughal period, one needs to keep in mind that it was a space for leisure, scholarship, culture and learning. To acknowledge that these women lived a life of relative luxury does not amount to stigmatising them as long as we recognise that they were also engaged on political, cultural, and economic fronts.⁴⁸¹

First Pādishāh Begum of the Mughal Empire: Āka-jānam Khānzādā Begum is an attempt to highlight that life in the Mughal Harem was not as one-dimensional as some recent depictions have led us to believe. Despite its secrecy and complexities, it is a much more dynamic space than how it is often characterised. Khānzādā Begum is just one of the many veiled women of this glorious and yet much-misunderstood institution. Hopefully, with greater research, we will soon be able to see beyond the "myth of harem" and study their inmates more empathetically.

⁴⁷⁹ Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 181–182.

⁴⁸⁰ The concept of active participation, as has been discussed by L. Balabanlilar, was unique to the Mughals: "Among them [the Mughals] remained a Timurid understanding of the rights and roles of elite women — not only with regard to their artistic production and patronage, but also, in marked contrast to their contemporaries, the Ottomans and the Safavids, the power offered to the young, even childless, royal women and their active participation in dynastic survival and political success." See "Mystic Feast," 123.

⁴⁸¹ I am grateful to Dr Mehreen Chida-Razvi for sharing her insight on the Mughal harem.

List of Illustrations

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Image 3: Courtesy of The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, Cora Timken Burnett Collection of Persian Miniatures and Other Persian Art Objects, Bequest of Cora Timken Burnett, 1956, accession number 57.51.29.

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Image 4: *Google Maps*, labelling by the author.

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Image 8: Courtesy of The Museum of Fine Arts, Boston, accession number 14.657, <https://collections.mfa.org/objects/148503/birth-of-prince->

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